

OF PRACTICE

Dibakar Pal,

*Retired Executive Magistrate (Civil Servant) &
 PhD Student, Department of Business Management,
 University of Calcutta, India*

ABSTRACT

Practice makes a man perfect. A doctor practises. A lawyer practises. As such both are not perfect. Both of them try to acquire perfection through practice. Thus they practise with imperfect knowledge. As a result many patients die and many clients lose their suits.

KEYWORDS: *Practice, perfect, imperfect, ideal*

INTRODUCTION

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Practice is the actual application or use of an idea, belief, or method, as opposed to theories relating to it e.g., the principles and practice of teaching. It is the customary, habitual, or expected procedure or way of doing of something. For example: Product placement is common practice in American movies.

Man practises. He has to practise. He is bound to practise. In this regard he has nothing

to do except practising. Thus man willy-nilly practises infinite times from cradle to coffin for the sake of his mere existence.

Practice makes a man perfect. A doctor practises. A lawyer practises. As such both are not perfect. Both of them try to acquire perfection through practice. Thus they practise with imperfect knowledge. As a result many patients die and many clients lose their suits. They say if a patient does not die a doctor cannot be a doctor. Similarly, a lawyer cannot be a lawyer until or unless a lawyer loses a suit. Thus death thrashes and loss crashes a doctor and a lawyer respectively and they become cautious accordingly.

A patient dies and a doctor gathers experience. Similarly, a lawyer loses the suit and be enriched both with act and tact. None knows how many deaths and how many lost suits will render both of them perfect. Then no death or no loss will occur in future. But in reality it does not happen at all. It is a fact that with the passage of time both death and loss become less. This is the outcome of experience and expertise. Also it is the outcome of practice and perfection as well.

Any learning of any lesson is complete only when a person can explain the cause of both the right and wrong answers of any question in question.

Perfect is alias and akin to ideal. Ideal is always unattainable. It is like infinity. None can reach infinity. Similarly, none can attain ideal. Further, ideal is as if divinity. To a mundane person divinity is a dream. Dream does not die even after death. Man tries to attain divinity since time immemorial. Only a sacred heart attains divinity.

There are numerous fields. Accordingly there are numerous practitioners. Each of them tries to develop. They are graded as per their achievement of expertise. With incomplete knowledge a medical practitioner becomes a quack. Similarly, a learner initially is an amateur. They are just like undeveloped, under developed, developing and developed country.

To be an expert thinking is a must. Thinking is alias and akin to physical pain. Very few persons can bear that pain. This answers why we see few successful experts around us. Through practice one becomes an expert. But an expert is not a perfectionist who is a rare genius. Thus all perfectionists are expert but all experts may not be perfectionist. It is like limit tends to infinity but never attains infinity as is found in calculus, a branch of Mathematics.

An expert suffers from superiority complex. In contrast a novice suffers from inferiority

complex. Complex of either kind is not good at all. The former one paves the way for untimely and ultimate downfall. The latter one is a hindrance for the full blooming of talent.

Now the question arises: who is an expert? They say, an expert is one who complicates simple things. Another school of thought defines; an expert is one who simplifies complex things. The former one may be called 'complex expert' and the later one as 'simple expert'. Then who is a novice? We may conclude, a novice is one who can neither complicate nor can he simplify anything.

The complex expert complicates anything to enjoy sadistic pleasure from the sufferings of people around him caused by complication created by him. He as well as everybody knows that only he can remove the complicity and thereby simplify the complex situation. He is so genius that he knows the solutions of any complex situation created or contributed by him or anybody. He is quite active as well as alert to maintain his demand of his expertise knowledge alive always. He does not play with straight bat. But straight batting is liked by the simple expert.

Simple expert is so callous and helpless that they become perplexed whenever situation is strange or does not favor them. Simple expert is optimist and simple by nature. They hate complexity and keep safe distance from the complexity of life and shrewd genius like complex expert. But life is not a bed of roses. Rather life appears with various problems, known or unknown, with greater dimension and magnitude as well. As such the demand of complex expert is ever increasing.

Someone believes in fate. Someone believes in effort. It seems fate is quite a mysterious factor. Sometimes fate dominates effort. For example: A brilliant student can score higher grade in the examination, but may not earn much as a doctor in spite of much effort. Thus a student may be successful in academic world but may not be so successful in professional life. This is equally true in case of a lawyer also. A brilliant barrister may be brief less in reality. Further, two shops may not have identical sell in spite of keeping identical products having equal price.

There is practice. Also there is malpractice. Defamed practice is called malpractice. It is ill famed either for its illegal motive or immoral essence or both simultaneously.

Practice is too good but malpractice is too bad. For good purpose man practises less and for bad purpose man malpractices long. It is human nature. In case of malpractice

monetary gain is instant. A shrewd practitioner enjoys sadistic pleasure cheating an innocent soul.

Man feels bored even practising a little. That very man enjoys much while is engaged in malpractice. In fact he is addicted in malpractice. He cannot sleep well without doing the mischievous deeds. In fact, immense is the attraction of forbidden things since time immemorial.

Practice has positive attitude. In contrast, malpractice is not only negative but detrimental in nature also. It allures a greedy person to earn money or achieve the desired thing illegally and early. The paradox is that short cut method cut short the life unexpectedly. Very few persons can avoid or ignore this greed.

Practice needs sincere attention. It demands much time. As such its outcome may not be instant. A good student reads attentively. He can answer all the questions in the examination. He can solve any future problem with his solid knowledge. Through sincere and serious study for long he builds up his career. If he fails once he should try repeatedly without surrendering to frustration. He must try till he reaches the desired goal.

An inattentive student malpractices in the examination. He tries to cheat the examiner. Sometimes he is caught red-handed and punished severely. He becomes a drop out. His career is finished premature. If he escapes, he cannot prosper in life with incomplete knowledge.

Practice has no substitute. It itself is its substitute. Its output is fine. Its outcome is permanent. A wise knows it. A fool knows it not. It seldom practises patiently. So it cannot finish any job. As such it cannot establish in life. He has to live on the mercy of others. Misfortune dogs him wherever he goes. Thus he suffers till he breaths his last. If someone tries for something there are two possibilities. Either he may fail or he may successfully fail to fail. A person should simply try for the later one. He must be always positive. He must be ambitious. If he is a proletariat he has nothing to lose except the chain.

Good track record of a player is achieved only after long practice. They say Rome was not built in a day. Nothing can be achieved overnight. Make up in the stage is not always possible by all. All cannot compensate deficiency. Only an intelligent person sometimes can do it. Consistently good academic or track record is not an easy matter. A good player

can score once. A great player can make hat trick. He can make hat trick in any field of home and abroad. They say where goodness ends greatness begins.

There are many faiths. There are many beliefs. Accordingly there are many practitioners as well. Religion is good. But its practitioners are bad. The world is the witness of many massacres in the name of religion.

No religion is bad. All the religions teach good lessons. But its followers seldom care for those moral lessons. They are blind. Sometimes they are blunt. They are interested about rituals seldom for religion. Essence of religion remains unknown to them. They are so unfortunate. They are so cursed.

The different sects are rivals with each other. Rivalry coupled with hatred provoke them to join in riots thus to establish individual supremacy. The majority compels the minority to convert. This conversion is done with the intention to drag all people under one umbrella with the malafide motif to keep only one religion in the world banishing all other faiths and beliefs. They intend to practise monopoly which is simply dictatorship. The tyrant practitioners are not ready to hear third voice. They are so intolerant. There may be choice, but their voice is final. In democracy there are many voices. They practise dictatorship. As such they impose their choice. Their master's voice is final. He is the big boss. He is the protagonist. He is the God father. Unlimited power render him intolerant. It is not good to study always. Similarly, it is not good to play day and night forgetting study. It is judicious to follow routine for both the engagements. In case of religion there is no such routine rather one can pray round the clock.

Practice becomes fruitful only when devotion is mingled with it. Inner urge is the chief ingredient that insists someone to practice that paves the way for sure and certain success.

CONCLUSION

Both good and bad persons practise. A thief practises how to steal and escape successfully. A police practises how to catch a thief. Here lies the uniqueness of practice rather than unique practice.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.